

Optimizing monthly solar PV tilt angles and energy yield across global climate zones: A hybrid machine learning and PVLlib approach

Ohn Zin Lin^{a,*}, Libor Štěpanec^a, Eftichios Koutroulis^b, Dagmar Juchelkova^a, Hnin Yee Aye^a

^a Department of Applied Electronics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava, 70800, Moravian-Silesian, Czech Republic

^b School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE), Technical University of Crete, Akrotiri Campus, Chania, 73100, Chania, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Photovoltaic systems
Optimal tilt angle
Machine learning
Solar energy forecasting
PVLlib simulation
Climate zone analysis

ABSTRACT

Accurate determination of photovoltaic (PV) tilt angles is essential for maximizing energy yield, yet traditional methods often rely on fixed or latitude-based empirical rules that overlook dynamic climatic factors. While machine learning (ML) has been applied for solar irradiance prediction and system optimization, few studies have directly targeted monthly tilt angle prediction. This paper presents a hybrid framework that integrates PVLlib-based simulations with supervised ML models to predict monthly optimal tilt angles for fixed PV installations across diverse climate zones. The framework uses simulated energy output as ground truth and trains models using localized features such as solar radiation, ambient temperature, humidity, and geographic data. Applied across 17 cities spanning tropical, dry, temperate, and continental climates, the Random Forest surrogate reproduced PVLlib-optimal monthly tilts with MAE $2.04 \pm 0.04^\circ$ and $R^2 0.975 \pm 0.001$ under 5-fold cross-validation (67,287 out-of-fold samples). Relative to Klein's fixed-tilt rule, ML-guided monthly tilts increased annual yield by a median 7.8 % (interquartile range 7.0–8.5 %), while the maximum gain was 12.2 % in Reykjavík. Statistical validation using paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests confirms the robustness of the approach. Results highlight ML's scalability and adaptability, offering a measurement-free alternative for climate-responsive PV design.

1. Introduction

PV systems are central to the global transition toward renewable energy. Among the key parameters influencing PV system performance, the tilt angle of solar panels is critical, as it determines the amount of solar irradiance incident on the module surface. Rehman et al. [1] emphasized the importance of tilt adjustment in maximizing PV performance across diverse climatic zones, highlighting its role in enhancing energy yield and system stability.

Traditional methods for determining optimal tilt angles, such as Klein's empirical formula [2] typically rely on fixed or seasonally adjusted angles based on latitude. While these methods are simple to apply and widely adopted in practice, they do not consider dynamic environmental variables such as changes in solar trajectory, cloud cover, and atmospheric transparency [3]. Moreover, it has been highlighted that multi-row PV fields require more sophisticated modeling due to irradiance degradation in subsequent rows and complex view factor effects, reinforcing the need for enhanced tilt and spacing considerations

in PV design [4].

Le Roux [5] demonstrated that PV systems with optimally fixed tilt angles in South Africa achieved up to 10 % more annual insolation than those installed horizontally, reinforcing the value of localized solar data for enhancing performance. In data-scarce environments, tilt angle estimation becomes more challenging. Chinchilla et al. [6], using irradiance data from over 2500 global sites, showed that tilt angles could be estimated using cubic regression even in the absence of local measurements, supporting the feasibility of statistical and machine learning models for generalized PV planning.

Recent advances in machine learning (ML) have enabled more accurate and location-sensitive tilt angle estimation. Rinchi et al. [7] developed a global ML model based on PVGIS data from over 12,000 sites, demonstrating that monthly meteorological data significantly improves predictive accuracy. To overcome the limitations of static empirical methods, researchers have increasingly explored data-driven approaches to improve PV system performance. ML, in particular, has shown considerable promise in areas such as solar radiation forecasting

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ohn.zin.lin@vsb.cz (O.Z. Lin).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.125163>

Received 27 June 2025; Received in revised form 11 November 2025; Accepted 29 December 2025

Available online 30 December 2025

0960-1481/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Table 1
Comparative analysis of recent prior machine learning approaches and the proposed study for solar PV optimization.

Paper	What is Calculated	Advantages	Disadvantages
[19]	ML-based solar irradiance prediction using Gaussian Regression and Grey Wolf Optimization	High accuracy in irradiance forecasting using a hybrid ML-optimization model; useful for enhancing distribution grid efficiency	Focuses only on irradiance; does not provide system-level design recommendations such as tilt optimization
[17]	Multi-orientation irradiance estimation using a hybrid physical-MLP model	Effectively combines physical modeling and deep learning to reconstruct irradiance across panel orientations; suitable for real-time estimation	Requires measured PV output data; limited in early-stage system design or in data-scarce environments
[7]	Global tilt angle prediction using ML and geospatial data	Global-scale tilt prediction using ML; useful for macro-level planning	Annual optimization only; lacks seasonal resolution and no energy validation
[14]	Optimum tilt and azimuth angles using climate-based empirical models for France and Italy	Provides validated empirical equations based on real climate data; considers azimuth influence and seasonal variation	Limited to two countries; lacks generalization and does not use ML or predictive adaptability
This Study	ML-based monthly optimal tilt angle prediction and energy output using PVLlib + supervised ML	Introduces a hybrid PVLlib + ML approach (Random Forest, XGBoost) to predict monthly optimal tilt angles using only weather and geographic features; validated across 17 cities in 4 climate zones; yields up to 12.2 % more energy vs. empirical formulas; statistically validated (MAE, R^2 , Wilcoxon)	Relies on PVLlib-simulated labels; generalizability may require retraining for extreme or unmodeled climatic conditions

[8], PV output prediction [9], and energy system optimization [10]. However, although ML has been increasingly applied, its use for predicting monthly optimal tilt angles across diverse climatic zones remains limited in scope.

This study proposes a hybrid framework that integrates PVLlib-based energy simulations with supervised machine learning models to predict monthly optimal tilt angles. Historical weather data from 17 cities spanning tropical, subtropical, temperate, and subpolar climate zones are used in combination with the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) [11], which provides Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) datasets. PVLlib is employed to simulate energy output for tilt angles ranging from 0° to 70°, and the configuration with the highest monthly energy yield is treated as the ground truth. These simulation results are then used to train three ML models such as Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression using meteorological and geographic features as predictors. The objectives of this study are the following.

- Develop a machine learning model to predict monthly optimal tilt angles using historical meteorological and solar irradiance data.
- Simulate PV energy output using PVLlib for a wide range of tilt angles across multiple global locations.
- Compare ML-based tilt angle predictions against traditional fixed and seasonal-tilt methods in terms of energy yield.

The work presented in this paper offers the following unique contributions.

- A hybrid method that combines PVLlib simulations with supervised ML models (Random Forest, XGBoost) to directly predict monthly optimal tilt angles, not just irradiance or output.
- Application across 17 cities spanning 4 climate zones, showing generalizability.
- Integration of climate-specific features, enabling accurate and scalable tilt optimization without relying on on-site measurements.
- Demonstration that ML-predicted tilt angles improve energy yield by up to 12.2 % compared to traditional methods like Klein's formula.
- Statistical validation (e.g., MAE, R^2 , Wilcoxon tests) confirming model reliability and superiority over traditional regression.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature on tilt angle optimization and machine learning applications in solar energy. Section 3 details the proposed methodology, including data collection, PVLlib simulation, and the ML workflow. Section 4 presents the results and discussion, covering tilt angle patterns, model performance, and energy yield comparisons. Section 5 concludes with a summary of findings, limitations, and directions for future work.

2. Literature review

PV module tilt strongly influences solar energy yield and grid-relevant power output characteristics. Recent study [12] emphasized that latitude and tracking configuration substantially affect annual energy production. Mayer [13] further highlighted that inappropriate tilt settings can significantly degrade forecasting accuracy, underscoring the importance of tilt-aware system design.

Conventional tilt selection techniques include fixed-angle rules (e.g., tilt \approx latitude) and seasonal adjustment formulas, which offer simplicity but do not fully account for local climatic variability, leading to sub-optimal yields in many regions [3,14]. Memme et al. [3] and Memme and Fossa [14] showed that monthly tilt adjustments can outperform fixed settings and that azimuth deviations from south-facing orientations can be advantageous under certain seasonal irradiance conditions. Similarly, Lu and Qin [8] found that regional climatic regimes substantially influence optimal tilt selection, supporting the case for dynamic or monthly tilt determination.

Traditional empirical irradiance models can perform well when

Fig. 1. Research gap and proposed solution: PVLlib-simulated monthly tilt labels combined with supervised ML using climate features.

locally calibrated, but they do not incorporate adaptive system design [15]. Recent work has therefore explored data-driven methods. For example, Singh et al. [16] integrated ML-based irradiance prediction with hybrid optimization, while Gao et al. [17] reconstructed orientation-specific irradiance by combining physical modeling and neural networks. Complementary techno-economic studies also show that tilt and azimuth selection can be optimized jointly for both yield and cost objectives [10]. Additionally, emerging ML models have demonstrated the feasibility of estimating tilt angles directly from climate and environmental features [18].

Despite advances in machine learning-based forecasting, a significant gap remains in the application of ML for dynamically optimizing PV tilt angles across diverse geographic and climatic regions. Most prior studies have focused on output-side predictions, such as solar radiation or PV power forecasting, or relied on fixed-angle or empirical configurations that do not adapt to local environmental variability. Few studies have utilized large-scale, simulation-derived tilt datasets as training inputs, nor evaluated ML-predicted tilt performance across global climate zones. Table 1 illustrates the comparative analysis with recent similar approaches. Moreover, Fig. 1 highlights the existing studies and proposed approach for this research.

This study addresses these gaps by generating monthly optimal tilt labels using PVLlib simulations and training supervised ML models that rely solely on meteorological and geographic features. The resulting framework enables scalable and climate-sensitive tilt optimization suitable for diverse global locations.

3. Methodology

This study combines simulation-based analysis with machine learning to predict monthly optimal tilt angles for PV systems. The methodology consists of three core components: (1) PV energy output simulation using PVLlib, (2) machine learning model development, and (3) model training and performance evaluation.

3.1. Workflow summary: simulation and machine learning integration

The flowchart in Fig. 2 illustrates the complete workflow adopted in this study for optimizing monthly PV tilt angles using machine learning and PV simulation. The process begins with the collection of historical weather data, including key variables such as solar irradiance (GHI, DNI, DHI), ambient temperature, wind speed, pressure, and humidity. This is followed by the definition of simulation parameters, where system settings such as location coordinates, PV module specifications, and tilt angle range (0° – 70°) are configured.

Using the PVLlib Python library, PV energy output simulations are then conducted across the full tilt angle range for each city and month. The results yield the optimal monthly tilt angles and corresponding energy outputs, which form the target values for the machine learning models.

In parallel, the simulation output undergoes data cleaning and pre-processing, filtering out non-sunshine hours and low-energy values to create a high-quality training dataset. The processed data is then used to train machine learning models (e.g., Random Forest, XGBoost) using features such as weather, time, and geographical information. These models are validated against simulation-derived tilt angles using metrics like MAE, RMSE, and R^2 .

After validation, the ML-predicted tilt angles are compared with those derived from the traditional Klein method, a widely used fixed-angle estimation formula based on latitude. Finally, the workflow concludes by quantifying the percentage energy gain achieved through ML-based tilt optimization and providing monthly tilt recommendations for improved PV system performance across diverse climate zones.

3.2. Simulation framework (PVLlib)

To determine the monthly optimal tilt angles, energy output simulations were performed using the PVLlib Python library [20], a widely used open-source toolkit for modeling photovoltaic (PV) energy systems.

Fig. 2. Workflow of the proposed approach.

The simulations were conducted for 17 globally distributed cities, selected to represent four Köppen–Geiger climate zones: tropical, subtropical, temperate, and cold/subpolar. These locations span both hemispheres and cover a wide range of latitudes to ensure climatic diversity and enhance the generalizability of the model. Fig. 3 provides the geographical coordinates, hemisphere classification, and Köppen climate codes for each selected city.

To facilitate interpretation of the climate codes presented in Fig. 3, Table 2 provides an overview of the Köppen–Geiger climate classification categories used in this study.

The PV system was configured with the following standardized parameters.

- PV module capacity: 100 kWp

- Surface azimuth: 0° (south-facing in the northern hemisphere; north-facing in the southern hemisphere)
- Module type: Glass-polymer (open rack)
- Losses: 14 %
- Temperature model: Sandia PV Array Performance Model (SAPM, open rack, glass-polymer)
- Inverter parameters: Nominal AC power matched to PV output (100 kW)

Hourly Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) weather data were retrieved for each location using the PVGIS API [11]. The dataset includes critical input variables such as global horizontal irradiance (GHI), direct normal irradiance (DNI), diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI), ambient temperature, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure. Energy

Fig. 3. Geographical and climate classification of Selected locations.

output simulations were conducted for tilt angles ranging from 0° to 70° in 1° increments. For each city and each month, the optimal tilt angle was identified as the one yielding the highest simulated energy output. Data periods span 2005–2023 across 17 cities; full coverage and record counts are provided in Supplement S1, Table S4.

3.2.1. PVLlib-based simulation and equations

The PV energy output simulations in this study were conducted using the PVLlib Python library [20], which implements standard solar radiation models and system performance equations. For each city, tilts were tested from 0° to 70° in 1° steps and the monthly energy was calculated. The optimal tilt is the angle that gives the highest monthly energy. Predictor features include monthly irradiance and weather summaries and basic site descriptors (e.g., latitude, hemisphere). Scaling/encoding is fit on the training set and applied to validation data only. Full equations, coefficients, and module/inverter settings are provided in Supplement S1.

Table 2 Geographical characteristics and Köppen climate classification of selected cities [21].

Code	Name	Description
Am	Tropical rainforest	Short dry season; driest month <60 mm but very wet monsoon.
Aw	Tropical savanna	Distinct dry season in winter
Cfa	Humid subtropical	Hot summers, mild winters, rainfall year-round
Cfb	Oceanic climate	Mild summers and winters; steady precipitation
Csb	Mediterranean	Warm, dry summers; mild, wet winters
Dwa	Humid continental (dry winter)	Cold winters, hot summers, dry winter
Dfb	Humid continental	Cold winters, no dry season
Dfc	Subarctic	Very cold winters, short cool summers
Cfc	Subpolar oceanic	Cooler version of oceanic; cold, wet, windy
BWh	Hot desert	Extremely dry, very hot summers
ET	Tundra	Cold, treeless, summer temperatures just above freezing

3.3. Machine learning workflow

To predict the monthly optimal tilt angle for PV modules, a supervised machine learning approach was adopted. For each location and month, PVLlib simulations sweep tilts 0–70° (1° step). The optimal tilt is the angle with the highest monthly energy. Memme & Fossa [14] also highlights that Monthly optimization can increase yield over annual fixed tilts. The approach is consistent with isotropic transposition validated for tilted surfaces in warm, arid regions studied by Rinchi et al. [7]. To train the model, a comprehensive feature set was constructed. This included three categories of predictors.

1. Meteorological features, such as solar irradiance components, air temperature, and wind speed;
2. Temporal information, such as the month of the year;

Table 3 Features used for machine learning prediction of optimal tilt angles.

Category	Feature Name	Description
Weather	temp_air	Air temperature (°C)
	relative_humidity	Relative humidity (%)
	ghi	Global Horizontal Irradiance (W/m ²)
	dni	Direct Normal Irradiance (W/m ²)
	dhi	Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (W/m ²)
	ir(h)	Infrared irradiance (horizontal)
	wind_speed	Wind speed (m/s)
	wind_direction	Wind direction (°)
	pressure	Atmospheric pressure (hPa)
	month	Month of the year (1–12)
Time	latitude	Latitude of the location
	longitude	Longitude of the location
Geographic	climate_Cold	One-hot encoded: 1 if Cold zone, else 0
	climate_Subtropical	One-hot encoded: 1 if Subtropical zone, else 0
	climate_Temperate	One-hot encoded: 1 if Temperate zone, else 0
Climate Category	climate_Tropical	One-hot encoded: 1 if Tropical zone, else 0

Table 4
Model configurations used in this study (no hyperparameter tuning).

Model	Library	Key Parameters	Remarks
Random Forest	scikit-learn	n_estimators = 100, random_state = 42	Ensemble of 100 trees; default settings for others
XGBoost Regressor	XGBoost	n_estimators = 100, random_state = 42, verbosity = 0	Fast boosting with moderate tree count
Linear Regression	scikit-learn	Default parameters	No regularization or tuning applied

3. Geographic data, including latitude, longitude, and climate zone classification.

The climate zone of each location was encoded using one-hot encoding for the four Köppen-Geiger zones covered in the study. The complete list of input features used for training is provided in Table 3.

Three machine learning models were evaluated in this study: Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression. These models were selected based on their robustness and strong performance in similar environmental prediction tasks. The implementation was carried out using the Scikit-learn and XGBoost Python libraries. Data wrangling was performed with Pandas, and visualizations were generated using Matplotlib. The combination of simulation-derived tilt labels and data-rich environmental features enabled the ML models to learn complex, non-linear relationships governing optimal PV tilt angles across time and space. Prior work (Rinchi et al. [7]) shows that monthly inputs (e.g., GHI, DHI, temperature) enable accurate global tilt prediction and that ensemble methods perform strongly, supporting the choices in the proposed work.

3.3.1. Machine learning models and equations

The monthly optimal tilt is predicted using three regressors: Linear Regression, Random Forest, and XGBoost. Model definitions and equations are provided in Supplement S1. Here, configurations and training protocol only are reported.

Models and settings (no hyperparameter tuning) are listed in Table 4. All models were trained on 80 % of the data and validated on the remaining 20 %.

3.4. Model training and validation

The models were evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation with shuffling (random_state = 42). In each fold, models train on four folds and are tested on the held-out fold. The out of fold (OOF) results are reported as mean \pm SD for MAE ($^\circ$), RMSE ($^\circ$), and R^2 (see Table 7). All preprocessing (e.g., scaling/encoding) is fit within the training fold and

applied to the held-out fold to avoid leakage. Model hyperparameters use library defaults (no tuning). For a secondary analysis, tilt is discretized into three bins: Low 0–29 $^\circ$, Medium 30–49 $^\circ$, High 50–70 $^\circ$. The accuracy and macro-F1, and inspect confusion matrices are reported in Table 9.

To assess transferability, the following studies are run.

- LOBO-CV (leave-one-biome-out), and
- LOCO-CV (leave-one-city-out) with a 250 km buffer to exclude nearby training samples. All transforms are fit on training splits only; metrics are computed on OOF predictions.

For the case study, XGBoost is trained on Berlin and used to predict monthly tilts for Ostrava; monthly energy is taken as the maximum over tilts 0–70 $^\circ$. Equations and metric definitions (e.g., R^2 , MAE, RMSE) are provided in Supplement S1.

4. Results & discussion

4.1. Monthly optimal tilt angles- simulation based

The monthly optimal tilt angles were determined using PVLib-based simulations for each of the 17 selected cities. These simulations calculated energy outputs across a tilt angle range of 0 $^\circ$ –65 $^\circ$ in 1 $^\circ$ increments. For each month, the tilt angle that resulted in the maximum simulated energy output was identified as the optimal angle. The results reveal seasonal variations in optimal tilt angles, particularly in locations further from the equator. Cities in tropical regions, such as Jakarta, exhibited relatively stable tilt values throughout the year, while cities in temperate and cold regions showed significant fluctuations, with higher tilt angles in winter months and lower ones in summer.

Fig. 4 shows strong seasonality in Helsinki, where summer favors flatter tilts (~15–30 $^\circ$) and winter favors steeper tilts (~50–65 $^\circ$), supporting seasonal or adaptive tilt. The Bangkok tilt–energy curve is provided in Supplement S1, Fig. S2 to show how tilt patterns vary with local climate and latitude.

Table 5 summarizes that the analysis of monthly optimal tilt angles across 17 globally distributed cities reveals clear trends influenced by climate zones and latitude. In tropical regions (Af, Aw, and equator-adjacent Cfb), such as Jakarta, Bangkok, and Nairobi, the optimal tilt angles remain consistently low throughout the year, typically ranging from 0 $^\circ$ to 20 $^\circ$. This stability reflects the relatively constant solar path in near-equatorial locations, where the sun's position does not vary drastically across seasons. As a result, fixed low-tilt PV installations are sufficient for maximizing energy output in these zones, and there is limited value in implementing seasonal or dynamic tilt adjustment strategies.

In contrast, cities in subtropical (BWh, Csb, Cfa), temperate (Dwa, Csa, Cfb, Dfb), and cold/subpolar zones (Cfc, Dfc, ET) exhibit increasing seasonal variability in optimal tilt angles. Subtropical cities like Dubai, Cape Town, and Sydney show moderate shifts between summer and winter, indicating that semi-annual tilt adjustments can improve performance. Temperate cities including Beijing, New York, and Berlin, display sharper seasonal contrast, with tilt angles ranging from low values (~5 $^\circ$ –15 $^\circ$) in summer to high values (>45 $^\circ$) in winter, justifying the adoption of seasonally adjustable systems. Cold and subpolar cities such as Helsinki, Reykjavík, and Ushuaia show the most dramatic tilt fluctuations (up to 70 $^\circ$ in winter), emphasizing the potential benefits of dual-tilt or automated tracking systems to maintain efficiency in environments with extreme solar angle variation.

These seasonal patterns also interact with non-ideal operating conditions, especially at very low POA tilt (β) where particulate build-up is not easily shed by gravity or rain. Ullah et al. highlight this effect: in a ~100-day Lahore study, soiling losses were ~26 % at $\beta = 0^\circ$, ~18 % at ~35 $^\circ$, and ~14 % at 90 $^\circ$, confirming that losses decrease with increasing tilt [22]. Consistent with this evidence, IEA-PVPS recommends a ~10 $^\circ$

Fig. 4. Monthly PV energy output in Helsinki simulated using PVLib.

Table 5
Monthly optimal tilt angles (in degrees) for photovoltaic systems in 17 globally distributed cities based on PVLib simulations.

City	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Bangkok	46	37	16	2	0	0	0	0	8	25	40	47
Beijing	63	51	40	19	10	6	7	14	30	48	60	65
Berlin	33	48	25	24	5	8	14	22	36	37	54	45
Cape Town	4	12	29	42	47	44	46	41	29	16	6	3
Dubai	46	34	22	10	2	0	1	6	20	36	48	50
Helsinki	49	28	35	20	19	14	16	24	32	26	50	59
Jakarta	0	0	4	20	30	38	39	29	12	0	0	0
Las Vegas	56	52	34	18	9	5	7	14	31	48	60	57
Madrid	49	44	38	14	10	7	9	17	32	44	56	60
Nairobi	0	0	2	14	20	21	16	14	4	0	0	0
New York City	52	46	32	18	9	7	9	15	28	46	53	52
Ostrava	48	28	30	13	4	5	10	15	25	34	42	34
Reykjavík	60	37	28	23	9	13	21	37	43	59	68	70
Santiago	5	13	29	45	53	42	48	21	28	15	7	4
Sydney	5	27	44	44	50	59	45	36	16	7	6	5
Tokyo	53	42	27	16	6	3	5	12	24	34	53	51
Ushuaia	14	21	33	47	46	34	40	50	44	31	15	12

Table 6
Seasonal classification of the 17 study cities by hemisphere and region.

Region	Example Cities	Summer Months	Winter Months	Seasonal Characteristics
Northern Hemisphere	Berlin, New York, Beijing, Madrid, Ostrava, Tokyo, Dubai, Las Vegas, Helsinki, Bangkok	April to October	November to March	Clear to strong seasonal variation depending on latitude [24]
Southern Hemisphere	Cape Town, Sydney, Santiago, Ushuaia	October to March	April to September	Opposite seasonal cycle; moderate to strong variation [25,26]
Equatorial Region	Nairobi, Jakarta	Rainy: Nov–Mar	Dry: Jun–Sep	Minimal solar variation; tilt remains relatively constant year-round [27]

Table 7
Cross-validated performance (5-fold CV). Metrics are computed from out-of-fold predictions and reported as mean ± SD across folds. Models use library defaults and cross-validation is for evaluation only (no tuning).

Model	Folds	N (OOF)	MAE (°) mean ± SD	RMSE (°) mean ± SD	R ² mean ± SD
Random Forest	5	67,287	2.04 ± 0.04	3.65 ± 0.09	0.975 ± 0.001
XGBoost	5	67,287	3.69 ± 0.06	5.36 ± 0.07	0.947 ± 0.002
Linear Regression	5	67,287	15.00 ± 0.10	18.56 ± 0.11	0.364 ± 0.010

minimum tilt to promote rain-driven self-cleaning. Below this threshold—particularly in hot, dry zones—arrays generally require regular manual/robotic cleaning [23]. Accordingly, for months in Table 7 where $\beta < 10^\circ$, the reported optima are valid under clean-surface assumptions, and practical designs typically either apply a $\sim 10^\circ$ minimum or plan routine cleaning to sustain yield.

4.2. Monthly optimal energy output - simulation based

To evaluate the performance of monthly tilt optimization, PV energy output across 17 cities was simulated using PVLib and compared against Klein's fixed-angle and seasonal tilt methods. The selected cities represent diverse climate zones and were categorized by hemisphere and regional characteristics, as summarized in Table 6. Seasonal periods were adjusted accordingly to account for differences between the Northern and Southern Hemispheres, while equatorial regions were classified based on rainy and dry seasons due to minimal solar angle variation.

4.2.1. Cold/high-latitude city in northern hemisphere: Reykjavík

Fig. 5 presents the energy output comparison in Reykjavík using three tilt strategies. As a subpolar, high-latitude city, Reykjavík experiences extreme seasonal shifts in solar elevation, with low solar angles and short days during winter. The PVLib-based monthly optimal tilt strategy provides substantial improvements, especially during the summer months when solar availability is higher and PV module

orientation plays a critical role.

Compared to Klein's fixed tilt at 30° , monthly optimization increases annual energy yield by up to 12.4%. The monthly percentage gains over the fixed tilt range from 1.5% (December) to 19.9% (June). Compared to the seasonal tilt method ($\pm 15^\circ$), gains range from 0.5% (January) to 10.7% (June). While Klein's seasonal method performs better than the fixed approach, it still lacks the granularity needed to capture monthly variations, especially in months with rapidly changing solar elevation angles. These results confirm that adaptive tilt optimization is especially valuable in high-latitude regions where seasonal variation is most pronounced. Even small improvements in winter can be meaningful in such

Fig. 5. Monthly PV energy output in Reykjavík using three tilt strategies. Significant performance gains are seen with monthly optimization in summer.

Fig. 6. Monthly energy output comparison for Cape Town using three tilt strategies. The results reflect strong seasonal variation, with simulation-based optimization showing clear performance gains during the Southern Hemisphere's winter months.

environments due to already limited solar resources.

4.2.2. Southern hemisphere region: Cape Town

Fig. 6 presents the monthly energy output for Cape Town using three tilt strategies: PVLib-simulated monthly optimal tilt, Klein's fixed tilt at 0°, and the seasonal tilt method (±15°). As a subtropical city in the Southern Hemisphere, Cape Town experiences marked seasonal variation, with its lowest solar elevations occurring between May and August.

The monthly optimal tilt strategy consistently outperforms both traditional methods throughout the year, with the most pronounced gains during the winter months (May–August). Compared to the fixed tilt, monthly optimization increases annual energy output by approximately 10.5 %, and by 4.8 % relative to the seasonal method.

The monthly energy gain over the fixed tilt ranges from 1.6 % (December) to 44.3 % (June), while the gain over the seasonal tilt ranges from 0.7 % (December) to 13.8 % (June). These substantial differences highlight the importance of monthly granularity, especially in mid-year months when fixed or seasonal settings underperform.

While Klein's seasonal method offers moderate improvements over the fixed tilt during winter, it fails to capture finer variations in solar elevation during transitional months such as April and September. These results underscore the value of adaptive tilt strategies in regions with strong seasonal solar angle variation, particularly in the Southern Hemisphere where solar path dynamics differ significantly from Northern Hemisphere cities.

4.2.3. Summary across all regions

Bangkok (tropical, Northern Hemisphere) and Nairobi (equatorial)

are provided in Supplement S1 (Fig. S3–S4) to illustrate hemispheric variation. The simulation results confirm that monthly tilt optimization improves annual PV energy output in all 17 study cities. The largest gains are observed in high-latitude regions such as Reykjavík and Helsinki, where annual increases exceed 12 % compared to fixed tilt configurations, due to pronounced seasonal solar angle variation. Cold and temperate cities like Berlin and Ostrava also show substantial improvements, typically above 8 %. In contrast, tropical and equatorial cities such as Nairobi and Jakarta yield more modest gains between 2 % and 5 %, reflecting limited solar elevation variability.

These findings underscore the value of adaptive tilt strategies, particularly those guided by machine learning or simulation models in regions with significant seasonal fluctuation. Such approaches offer a scalable path for enhancing PV system efficiency worldwide. Furthermore, in dust-prone environments, tilt angle optimization becomes even more critical. For example, Ullah et al. [22] reported that quarterly tilt adjustments in Lahore improved energy output by 6.6 %, while flat-panel configurations suffered up to 26 % energy loss due to dust accumulation. This highlights the dual importance of seasonal adaptation and environmental responsiveness in PV system design.

4.3. Machine learning model performance

The machine learning models were trained and evaluated on a dataset comprising 67,287 samples, derived from PVLib simulations across 17 cities and 12 months, covering a tilt angle range from 0° to 70°. Each sample includes 16 input features (see Table 4), encompassing meteorological variables (e.g., GHI, DNI, temperature, humidity), time indicators (e.g., month), and geographical attributes (e.g., latitude, climate zone). The dataset was randomly split into 80 % for training and 20 % for testing, and all models were trained using default hyperparameters unless otherwise stated.

Fig. 7 compares the predictive performance of Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression models. The red dashed diagonal indicates perfect agreement between predicted and simulation-derived tilt

Table 8

Paired comparisons of per-instance OOF absolute errors across identical 5-fold splits. All comparisons remain significant after Bonferroni correction for three tests ($\alpha_{adj} = 0.0167$).

Model Pair	Paired t-test p-value	Wilcoxon p-value
RF vs XGB	<0.00001	<0.00001
RF vs LR	<0.00001	<0.00001
XGB vs LR	<0.00001	<0.00001

Fig. 7. Comparison of predicted tilt angles from machine learning models (Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression) with simulation-derived optimal tilt angles. The red dashed line indicates the ideal prediction line ($y = x$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 9

Classification performance for all climate zones using the Random Forest model. Performance metrics include precision, recall, F1-score, and class support (number of samples).

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Low (0°–20°)	0.96	0.98	0.97	7164
Medium-low (21°–40°)	0.86	0.81	0.83	2619
Medium-high (41°–60°)	0.86	0.85	0.86	2257
High (61°–70°)	0.91	0.92	0.92	1418

angles. Metrics shown here correspond to a single 80/20 held-out test split used for illustration purposes. Random Forest exhibited the best fit, achieving an R^2 of 0.9705 and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 2.29°, indicating strong agreement with PVLib-generated ground truth.

These findings are consistent with the previous research, which showed that Random Forest rivaled heuristic optimization methods such as genetic algorithms in urban East Asian settings, achieving superior tilt prediction performance [28,29]. Similarly, the studies found that Random Forest outperformed empirical models across Southeast Asia when trained on monthly GHI, DNI, and cloud cover inputs [30,31]. Moreover, Barbón et al. [32] observed that deviations within $\pm 10^\circ$ from the optimal tilt result in negligible energy loss ($< 1\%$), reinforcing the robustness and feasibility of ML-derived tilt angles in real-world rooftop applications. Finally, Chinchilla et al. [6] noted that tilt deviations within $\pm 3^\circ$ typically result in $< 1\%$ energy loss, validating that minor ML prediction errors still yield near-optimal performance even in the absence of precise site-level data.

Table 7 reports 5-fold cross-validated, out-of-fold performance for

three surrogates that predict the PVLib-optimal tilt from site/climate features. Random Forest (RF) attains the lowest error (MAE = $2.04 \pm 0.04^\circ$, RMSE = $3.65 \pm 0.09^\circ$, $R^2 = 0.975 \pm 0.001$ over $N = 67,287$ OOF samples) indicating a very close approximation to the physics-based optimum. XGBoost (XGB) is competitive (MAE $3.69 \pm 0.06^\circ$, RMSE $5.36 \pm 0.07^\circ$, $R^2 = 0.947 \pm 0.002$) and clearly outperforms Linear Regression (LR) (MAE $15.00 \pm 0.10^\circ$, RMSE $18.56 \pm 0.11^\circ$, $R^2 = 0.364 \pm 0.010$), underscoring the need for non-linear models. The small fold-to-fold SDs reflect stable generalization rather than reliance on a particular split. All models use library defaults with no hyperparameter tuning. Therefore, the differences observed reflect intrinsic model capacity. These rankings are consistent with the paired significance tests summarized in Table 8. A 10-fold robustness check is provided in Supplement S1 (Table S5) and yields similar model order and error ranges.

To statistically compare models, two-sided paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were applied to per-sample OOF absolute errors from the same 5-fold splits. As shown in Table 8, all pairwise differences are highly significant ($p < 1 \times 10^{-5}$), confirming the RF > XGB > LR ranking observed in Table 8.

Beyond aggregate CV accuracy, geographic transferability was assessed next using leave-one-biome-out and leave-one-city-out evaluations. Using leave-one-biome-out (LOBO) splits, models trained on non-target biomes generalized well to Temperate and Cold and Subtropical regimes (e.g., XGB MAE $\approx 5.8\text{--}7.3^\circ$, RF MAE $\approx 6.4\text{--}8.8^\circ$, with $R^2 \approx 0.71\text{--}0.89$), while Tropical held-out performance degraded (MAE $\approx 14\text{--}19^\circ$, $R^2 < 0$), indicating limited extrapolation without in-domain data. Leave-one-city-out (LOCO) with a 250-km buffer showed strong spatial transfer to nearby but unseen cities (e.g., XGB MAE $\approx 7.2^\circ$, $R^2 \approx$

Fig. 8. Comparison of model prediction errors across Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB), and Linear Regression (LR).

Fig. 9. MAE of tilt angle predictions for 17 cities, grouped by climate zone. Tropical and subtropical regions show lower prediction errors, while cold-zone cities exhibit higher MAE due to greater seasonal variability.

Fig. 10. Top 10 most important input features for predicting monthly optimal tilt angles, as determined by the Random Forest model. Temporal (month), direct irradiance (DNI), and temperature (Temp_air) features showed the highest influence.

0.814; RF MAE $\approx 7.5^\circ$, $R^2 \approx 0.762$). Detailed per-biome and per-city results are provided in [Table S1](#) and [Table S2](#), with an overall summary in [Table S3](#).

Across 5-fold CV, Random Forest (RF) is the most accurate (e.g., $R^2 \approx 0.97$, MAE ≈ 2.0 – 2.3° ; [Table 8](#)), with XGBoost (XGB) close behind. To illustrate city-level transferability, a nearby-city case study is presented with XGB (Berlin→Ostrava): the ML monthly PV tilts closely track the PVLib-optimal tilts (MAE = 1.25° , RMSE = 2.04°), and the mean relative energy gap is 3.4 % ([Fig. S1](#)). Using XGB in this figure demonstrates that the conclusions are robust to the choice of model; an RF version yields nearly identical curves. Consistently, the LOBO/LOCO analyses ([Table S1–S3](#)) show strong generalization for both RF and XGB, with clear advantages over Linear Regression.

[Fig. 8](#) provides complementary insights into the comparative performance of the three machine learning models. The boxplot (left panel) shows that the Random Forest (RF) model has the narrowest inter-quartile range and the fewest extreme outliers, indicating stable and reliable error distributions. The bar plot (right panel) reinforces this by showing that RF achieves the lowest mean absolute error, accompanied by tight 95 % confidence intervals, underscoring its predictive consistency.

In contrast, the Linear Regression (LR) model displays higher average errors and greater dispersion, suggesting increased variance and reduced precision. The XGBoost (XGB) model performs better than LR, but still falls short of RF in both error magnitude and stability.

Together, these results validate the superior performance of ensemble-based models, particularly Random Forest, for predicting optimal solar PV tilt angles. The findings are consistent with statistical tests (paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, $p < 0.00001$), confirming that RF offers the most statistically robust and practically reliable solution across varying climatic conditions.

[Fig. 9](#) visualizes the MAE across the 17 cities using Random Forest, grouped by climate zone. Cities in colder, high-latitude regions—such as Ushuaia, Reykjavík, and Helsinki—show higher errors (1.4° – 2.0°), likely due to complex seasonal dynamics and rapid shifts in solar angles. In contrast, tropical and subtropical cities (e.g., Nairobi, Dubai, Jakarta, Bangkok) yield lower errors (below 1.0°), reflecting more stable solar geometries.

Key observations include.

- Nairobi achieved the lowest MAE ($\sim 0.75^\circ$), reflecting strong performance in equatorial settings with minimal seasonal change.
- Temperate cities (e.g., Berlin, Tokyo, Beijing) show intermediate errors ($\sim 1.1^\circ$), reflecting moderate seasonal variability.

- High-latitude cities (e.g., Ushuaia, Reykjavík) exhibited the highest MAE due to extreme solar elevation shifts and abrupt daylight transitions.

These findings highlight the role of climate and latitude in ML model performance. While minor prediction deviations remain within tolerable ranges, the results confirm that Random Forest is a scalable and robust surrogate for simulation-based tilt angle estimation and is adopted for all subsequent analyses in this study.

4.3.1. Feature importance analysis for tilt angle prediction

[Fig. 10](#) presents the top 10 most influential features in predicting monthly optimal tilt angles based on Random Forest's feature importance ranking. Temporal and irradiance-related variables dominate the list. The month feature ranks highest, highlighting the importance of seasonal patterns in solar geometry. Direct normal irradiance (DNI) and air temperature follow closely, indicating their strong influence on solar capture efficiency and thermal effects.

Latitude is the most impactful geographic feature, aligning with its fundamental role in determining the sun's angle. This finding is supported by Bahrami et al., [33] who demonstrated that latitude significantly affects solar tracking system performance and optimal tilt configurations, with tracking-related energy gains ranging from 17 % to 31 % across Europe and Africa. These results reinforce the critical value of incorporating geographic latitude into tilt angle prediction models.

Other important variables include infrared irradiance, global horizontal irradiance (GHI), pressure, and diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI). The presence of climate category indicators (e.g., climate_Cold) and longitude suggests minor yet region-specific adjustments that further enhance model performance.

4.3.2. Classification accuracy

The classification model demonstrated strong performance in predicting optimal tilt angle categories across all climate zones. Using a Random Forest classifier trained on environmental and geographic features, the model achieved an overall accuracy of 92 % on the test dataset. The tilt angles were grouped into four practical classes: Low (0° – 20°), Medium-low (21° – 40°), Medium-high (41° – 60°), and High (61° – 70°), each reflecting typical installation strategies across climatic regions.

Table 10

Average annual energy output (kWh/m²) for solar PV systems across 17 cities, comparing tilt strategies. The percentage gain represents the relative improvement of the ML approach over Klein's fixed method.

City	Klein Fixed (kWh/year)	Klein Seasonal (kWh/year)	ML Predicted (kWh/year)	% Gain Klein Fixed	Energy Improvement (kWh/year per 1 kW _p)
Bangkok	1518.7	1582.0	1636.5	7.8	117.8
Beijing	1654.7	1709.6	1770.5	7.0	115.8
Berlin	1005.0	1035.6	1090.2	8.5	85.2
Cape Town	1820.7	1714.0	1949.5	7.1	128.8
Dubai	1599.2	1646.8	1690.8	5.7	91.6
Helsinki	896.4	861.4	993.2	10.8	96.8
Jakarta	1416.7	1365.8	1488.8	5.1	72.1
Las Vegas	1956.7	2028.9	2116.9	8.2	160.2
Madrid	1936.1	2002.4	2083.8	7.6	147.7
Nairobi	2158.9	2074.8	2200.5	1.9	41.6
New York City	1484.6	1534.3	1599.7	7.8	115.1
Ostrava	915.4	942.0	993.2	8.5	77.8
Reykjavík	994.1	997.7	1115.3	12.2	121.2
Santiago	1842.9	1734.2	1987.3	7.8	144.4
Sydney	1440.7	1401.2	1549.6	7.6	108.9
Tokyo	1375.3	1421.3	1468.4	6.8	93.1
Ushuaia	1126.3	738.8	1224.3	8.7	98.0

The results presented in Table 9 demonstrate robust classification performance across all tilt angle categories. The Low tilt class (0° – 20°) achieved the highest performance, with a precision of 0.96, recall of 0.98, and an F1-score of 0.97. This suggests the model effectively captures conditions favoring flat or near-horizontal PV installations, which are common in equatorial or high-irradiance environments. Similarly, the High tilt class (61° – 70°) performed strongly with an F1-score of 0.92, indicating the model's reliability in recognizing scenarios requiring steep tilt angles, typical of higher latitudes or winter-optimized configurations.

Slightly lower performance was observed in the Medium-low (21° – 40°) and Medium-high (41° – 60°) categories, with F1-scores of 0.83 and 0.86, respectively. This modest drop in classification accuracy is likely due to overlapping environmental features in transitional zones or temperate climates, particularly during shoulder months. Misclassifications were primarily concentrated between these two mid-range categories, reflecting the inherent challenge of distinguishing tilt angles with narrower functional margins. The macro-averaged precision and recall were 0.90 and 0.89, respectively, confirming balanced performance across classes. The weighted averages, which account for class imbalance, aligned closely with overall model accuracy, reaffirming the classifier's robustness, even in the presence of a dominant class such as the Low tilt category.

These findings highlight the feasibility of supervised machine learning for dynamic or semi-dynamic solar tilt optimization, especially when integrated with real-time or seasonal forecasting data. The high classification accuracy, particularly for the extreme tilt categories, underscores the potential for deploying ML-based decision support tools in both grid-connected and off-grid PV systems.

To further improve classification performance, particularly in mid-range tilt categories, future work should consider.

- Incorporating additional features such as solar zenith angle, clearness index, or seasonal irradiance trends;
- Applying probabilistic classification or soft-labeling techniques to better handle ambiguous cases;
- Developing climate zone-specific models to enhance regional prediction accuracy.

4.4. Energy output and gain comparison by machine learning

This section presents a comparative analysis of annual energy output from solar PV systems using three tilt optimization strategies across 17 cities worldwide.

1. Klein's Fixed Tilt – A traditional method that sets the tilt equal to the site's absolute latitude.
2. Klein's Seasonal Tilt – An enhancement that adjusts tilt based on the time of year: latitude $+15^{\circ}$ in winter, latitude in spring/fall, and latitude -15° in summer.
3. ML-Based Optimal Tilt – A dynamic monthly optimization strategy. Optimal tilt angles were first simulated using PVLib for each month and then learned via a Random Forest regression model, enabling scalable deployment through prediction.

Table 10 summarizes the average annual energy output (kWh/m^2) per city under each strategy and shows the percentage gain achieved by the ML-assisted method over the Klein fixed tilt. The ML-based tilt strategy consistently outperforms the conventional methods across all studied locations. The highest gain was observed in Reykjavík (12.2 %), which highlights the effectiveness of machine learning in high-latitude regions where seasonal solar angle variation is extreme.

These findings are further supported by Ruan et al. [34], who developed a region-specific optimization model for high-latitude cold regions based on historical weather big data. Their approach demonstrated superior accuracy over conventional tilt formulas and

emphasized the importance of seasonal irradiance variation in determining optimal tilt configurations in polar and subpolar climates. Moderate gains were seen in cities like Bangkok and Jakarta, where solar geometry is relatively consistent throughout the year. Even in Nairobi, where performance is least sensitive to tilt angle, the ML approach still provided a measurable benefit (1.9 %). Over all 17 cities, the mean relative gain over Klein fixed is 7.6 % (median 7.8 % and interquartile range (IQR) 7.0–8.5 %), while 15/17 cities are below 9 %, with only Helsinki (10.8 %) and Reykjavík (12.2 %) at or above 9 %. These results demonstrate that machine learning models trained on simulated optimal tilts can generalize well across regions and provide location- and time-specific energy optimization, supporting the deployment of smarter and more adaptive solar tracking or manual tilt adjustment systems.

5. Conclusion and future work

This study presents a hybrid framework that integrates PVLib simulations with supervised machine learning to optimize monthly tilt angles for PV systems across diverse global climate zones. PVLib was used to simulate energy output across a tilt angle range of 0° – 70° for 17 representative cities, generating monthly optimal tilt configurations that served as ground truth for training machine learning models. Among the tested models, Random Forest delivered the best performance under 5-fold cross-validation, achieving MAE $2.04 \pm 0.04^{\circ}$ and $R^2 0.975 \pm 0.001$, outperforming XGBoost (MAE $3.69 \pm 0.06^{\circ}$, $R^2 0.947 \pm 0.002$) and Linear Regression (MAE $15.00 \pm 0.10^{\circ}$, $R^2 0.364 \pm 0.010$). Replacing traditional empirical rules (e.g., Klein's fixed or seasonal tilts) with ML-predicted monthly angles produced consistent annual yield gains — median 7.8 % (IQR 7.0–8.5 %) — with the largest relative improvements at high latitudes (Reykjavík 12.2 %, Helsinki 10.8 %).

The machine learning model demonstrated strong adaptability across different climate zones. In tropical locations such as Jakarta and Nairobi, where seasonal variation is minimal, the model achieved the lowest prediction errors, typically below 1° . In contrast, subpolar cities exhibited higher MAE values, close to 2° , due to more complex seasonal dynamics. Feature importance analysis identified month, direct normal irradiance (DNI), and air temperature as the most influential variables in predicting optimal tilt. Additionally, when tilt angles were grouped into four practical categories, the Random Forest classifier achieved over 92 percent accuracy, reliably identifying appropriate tilt ranges under varying environmental conditions.

It is important to clarify that the machine learning model was not designed to perform an independent optimization. PVLib remains the physics reference used to compute energy-tilt curves and define the optimal-tilt labels. The proposed ML model is a surrogate, not an independent optimizer: it approximates PVLib-optimal tilt from site/climate features, delivering near-optimal predictions at scale (Table 7). In practice, PVLib is preferred for single-site, design-stage analysis with full inputs, whereas the ML surrogate is advantageous for large-area mapping, rapid screening, or when only monthly/statistical data are available.

Future research should explore real-time integration of weather and irradiance data from IoT sensors to support dynamic tilt adjustment. Reinforcement learning could also be applied to enable autonomous, self-optimizing PV systems. Further work is needed to test the framework in utility-scale solar farms and to evaluate the economic trade-offs between ML-guided tilt optimization and traditional tracking systems. Finally, the applicability of this method should be assessed in diverse microclimates, including urban and rural PV installations, to ensure robustness across a wide range of deployment scenarios.

In addition, tilt-angle optimization was addressed using a supervised ML surrogate trained on PVLib-derived optimal-tilt labels. Across 17 cities and four climate zones, the surrogate attains high accuracy (Table 7) and scales to large-area mapping without rerunning per-tilt simulations. By leveraging climate-sensitive features, it provides monthly tilt recommendations when only monthly/statistical inputs are

available, thus improving over empirical latitude/seasonal rules while remaining consistent with the physics reference. Transfer tests (LOBO/LOCO) indicate robust generalization across mid-latitude biomes and to nearby unseen cities (Table S1–S3).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ohn Zin Lin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Libor Štěpánek:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **Eftichios Koutroulis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Dagmar Juchelkova:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Hnin Yee Aye:** Validation, Software, Investigation.

Data statement

The dataset used in this study is openly available on Zenodo under a CC BY 4.0 license at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17570100>.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT4 to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and assumed full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Given his role as Associate Editor, Eftichios Koutroulis had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science at the Technical University of Ostrava for their financial support. This work is supported under the project "Research Platform for Digital Transformation and Society 5.0, CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0012599" within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program, both funded by the European Regional Development Fund. We also extend our thanks to the University for providing the essential resources and facilities required to carry out this research. Special thanks are due to the Dean and the Head of the Department for their invaluable assistance and insightful feedback, which greatly enhanced the quality of this manuscript. Lastly, we would like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their thorough evaluations and constructive comments, which significantly contributed to the refinement of this article.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.125163>.

References

- [1] T. Rehman, M.A. Qaisrani, M.B. Shafiq, Y.F. Baba, N. Aslfattahi, A. Shahsavari, T. A. Cheema, C.W. Park, Global perspectives on advancing photovoltaic system performance—A state-of-the-art review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 207 (2025) 114889, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114889>.
- [2] S.A. Klein, Calculation of monthly average insolation on tilted surfaces, *Sol. Energy* 19 (1977) 325–329, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X\(77\)90001-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X(77)90001-9).
- [3] S. Memme, M. Fossa, D. Rousse, Best tilt of PV system in Canada: effect of the sky radiation model and climate conditions, *Renew. Energy* (2025) 123716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123716>.
- [4] S.Y. Alsadi, Y.F. Nassar, Estimation of solar irradiance on solar fields: an analytical approach and experimental results, *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* 8 (2017) 1601–1608, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSTE.2017.2697913>.
- [5] W.G. Le Roux, Optimum tilt and azimuth angles for fixed solar collectors in South Africa using measured data, *Renew. Energy* 96 (2016) 603–612, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.05.003>.
- [6] M. Chinchilla, D. Santos-Martín, M. Carpintero-Rentería, S. Lemon, Worldwide annual optimum tilt angle model for solar collectors and photovoltaic systems in the absence of site meteorological data, *Appl. Energy* 281 (2021) 116056, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116056>.
- [7] B. Rinchi, R. Dababseh, M. Jubran, S. Al-Dahidi, M.E.B. Abdalla, O. Ayadi, Global prediction of optimal solar panel tilt angles via machine learning, *Appl. Energy* 382 (2025) 125322, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.125322>.
- [8] N. Lu, J. Qin, Optimization of tilt angle for PV in China with long-term hourly surface solar radiation, *Renew. Energy* 229 (2024) 120741, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120741>.
- [9] J. Nunes Maciel, J. Javier Gimenez Ledesma, O. Hideo Ando Junior, Hybrid prediction method of solar irradiance applied to short-term photovoltaic energy generation, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 192 (2024) 114185, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114185>.
- [10] R. Bakhshi-Jafarabadi, C.D. Dinga, Optimum tilt and azimuth of fixed grid-connected photovoltaic system for peak load shaving: a multi-scale model, *Renew. Energy* (2025) 123714, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123714>.
- [11] European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Photovoltaic geographical information system (PVGIS). https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/pvgis_en, 2025. (Accessed 18 April 2025).
- [12] A. Gedifew, A. Benor, Evaluating the impact of tilt angles and tracking mechanisms on photovoltaic modules in Ethiopia, *Front. Energy Res.* 12 (2025) 1519725, <https://doi.org/10.3389/feng.2024.1519725>.
- [13] M.J. Mayer, Impact of the tilt angle, inverter sizing factor and row spacing on the photovoltaic power forecast accuracy, *Appl. Energy* 323 (2022) 119598, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119598>.
- [14] S. Memme, M. Fossa, Maximum energy yield of PV surfaces in France and Italy from climate based equations for optimum tilt at different azimuth angles, *Renew. Energy* 200 (2022) 845–866, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.10.019>.
- [15] J.L. De Souza, G.B. Lyra, C.M. Dos Santos, R.A. Ferreira Junior, C. Tiba, G.B. Lyra, M.A.M. Lemes, Empirical models of daily and monthly global solar irradiation using sunshine duration for Alagoas state, Northeastern Brazil, *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assessments* 14 (2016) 35–45, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2016.01.002>.
- [16] K. Singh, K.D. Mistry, H.G. Patel, Optimizing power loss in mesh distribution systems: Gaussian Regression Learner Machine learning-based solar irradiance prediction and distributed generation enhancement with Mono/Bifacial PV modules using Grey Wolf Optimization, *Renew. Energy* 237 (2024) 121590, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121590>.
- [17] Y. Gao, H. Ma, J. Zheng, W. Liu, F. Chen, L. Fan, H. Wang, W. Liu, X. Zhang, Reconstructing multi-orientation irradiance via PV panels: an isotropic Physical-MLP hybrid model, *Renew. Energy* 241 (2025) 122346, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.122346>.
- [18] T.C. Carneiro, P.A.C. Rocha, P.C.M. Carvalho, L.M. Fernández-Ramírez, Ridge regression ensemble of machine learning models applied to solar and wind forecasting in Brazil and Spain, *Appl. Energy* 314 (2022) 118936, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.118936>.
- [19] U. Singh, S. Singh, S. Gupta, M.A. Alotaibi, H. Malik, Forecasting rooftop photovoltaic solar power using machine learning techniques, *Energy Rep.* 13 (2025) 3616–3630, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejy.2025.03.005>.
- [20] W.F. Holmgren, C.W. Hansen, M.A. Mikofski, Pvlib python: a python package for modeling solar energy systems, *JOSS* 3 (2018) 884, <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00884>.
- [21] M. Kotteck, J. Grieser, C. Beck, B. Rudolf, F. Rubel, World Map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated, *Metz* 15 (2006) 259–263, <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2006/0130>.
- [22] A. Ullah, H. Imran, Z. Maqsood, N.Z. Butt, Investigation of optimal tilt angles and effects of soiling on PV energy production in Pakistan, *Renew. Energy* 139 (2019) 830–843, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.02.114>.
- [23] G. Friesen, W. Herrmann, G. Belluardo, B. Herteleer, G. Friesen, U. Jahn, Photovoltaic Module Energy Yield Measurements: Existing Approaches and Best Practice, International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Power Systems Programme, IEA PVPS), 2018. https://iea-pvps.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Photovoltaic_Module_Energy_Yield_Measurements_Existing_Approaches_and_Best_Practice_by_Task_13.pdf.
- [24] F. Su, W. Wang, A.G. Burns, X. Yue, F. Zhu, J. Lin, Statistical behavior of the longitudinal variations of daytime electron density in the topside ionosphere at middle latitudes, *JGR Space Physics* 121 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JA023029>.
- [25] D. Kotova, Y. Jin, W. Miloch, Interhemispheric variability of the electron density and derived parameters by the Swarm satellites during different solar activity, *J. Space Weather Space Clim.* 12 (2022) 12, <https://doi.org/10.1051/swsc/2022007>.
- [26] A.I.S. Farid, A.Sh.M. Elshoukrofy, A.A. Aly, A. Fathy, The climatology of the ionospheric electron density peak parameters retrieved from the two COSMIC

- missions between 2007-2023. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5363039/v1>, 2024.
- [27] W.H. Choong, N.B. Ariffin, H.P. Yoong, B.L. Chua, M.K.M. Shah, Characteristics Study of fresnel lens performance for solar concentration application, in: M. Chen, M. Giorgetti, B. Jin, R.K. Agarwal (Eds.), *Advances in Transdisciplinary Engineering*, IOS Press, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3233/ATDE230566>.
- [28] G.Y. Kim, D.S. Han, Z. Lee, Solar Panel tilt angle optimization using machine learning model: a case Study of Daegu City, South Korea, *Energies* 13 (2020) 529, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13030529>.
- [29] P.W. Khan, Y.-C. Byun, S.-J. Lee, Optimal photovoltaic Panel direction and tilt angle prediction using stacking ensemble learning, *Front. Energy Res.* 10 (2022) 865413, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2022.865413>.
- [30] C. He, J. Liu, F. Xu, T. Zhang, S. Chen, Z. Sun, W. Zheng, R. Wang, L. He, H. Feng, Q. Yu, J. He, Improving solar radiation estimation in China based on regional optimal combination of meteorological factors with machine learning methods, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 220 (2020) 113111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2020.113111>.
- [31] F. Liu, X. Wang, F. Sun, H. Wang, Correct and remap solar radiation and photovoltaic power in China based on machine learning models, *Appl. Energy* 312 (2022) 118775, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.118775>.
- [32] A. Barbón, C. Bayón-Cueli, L. Bayón, C. Rodríguez-Suanzes, Analysis of the tilt and azimuth angles of photovoltaic systems in non-ideal positions for urban applications, *Appl. Energy* 305 (2022) 117802, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117802>.
- [33] A. Bahrami, C.O. Okoye, U. Atikol, The effect of latitude on the performance of different solar trackers in Europe and Africa, *Appl. Energy* 177 (2016) 896–906, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.05.103>.
- [34] T. Ruan, F. Wang, M. Topel, B. Laumert, W. Wang, A new optimal PV installation angle model in high-latitude cold regions based on historical weather big data, *Appl. Energy* 359 (2024) 122690, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122690>.